

Spectrophotometric Determination of Atrazine [2-Chloro-4-ethylamino-6-isopropylamino-*s*-triazine] using *p*-Aminobenzoic Acid and its Applications

JOYCE VANISHA DAS and V. K. GUPTA*

School of Studies in Chemistry, Pt. Ravishankar Shukla University, Raipur-492 010

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Atrazine [2-chloro-4-ethylamino-6-isopropylamino-*s*-triazine] is a selective pre- and post-emergence herbicide. A large number of instrumental methods such as chromatography¹ and differential pulse polarography² have been reported for its determination. Very few reagents such as ethyl cyanoacetate³ and picric acid⁴ are used for the colorimetric determination of atrazine. Other methods are based on those reported for simazine⁵.

Here, a new and sensitive method is reported for the determination of atrazine. The method is based on Konig reaction, reported earlier for simazine⁵, cyanide⁶ and acrylonitrile⁷.

Atrazine is converted into a quaternary pyridinium halide by reacting it with pyridine, which undergoes addition of hydroxyl group in the presence of alkali to form a carbinol base. Further breaking of heterocyclic linkage takes place giving glutaconic dialdehyde. Finally, glutaconic dialdehyde couples with *p*-aminobenzoic acid in acidic medium to form a yellow-orange polymethine dye.

Results and Discussion

The colour system showed maximum absorption at 460 nm, where the reagent blank had negligible absorbance. Beer's law was obeyed over the range of 0.5-2.0 ppm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $8.1 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.003 \text{ } \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively.

Under optimum condition, 0.2 ml of pyridine, 1 ml of 2 M NaOH and 2 ml of *p*-aminobenzoic acid were sufficient for complete colour development.

Maximum colour intensity was observed when the solution containing pyridine was heated for 15 min on a boiling water bath and then allowed to cool. The coloured dye was stable for ~35 min at 15-30°. Polymethine dye was formed only under acidic conditions in the pH range 2.0-2.5. Precision of the method was checked by analysing 10 μg of atrazine in 10 ml of final solution for a period of 7 days. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were ± 0.007 and $\pm 1.9\%$ respectively.

The effects of some chemicals and ions in a standard solution containing 10 μg of atrazine per 10 ml causing an error of $\pm 2\%$ in absorbance values, were studied and the tolerance limits (ppm) were as follows : ethanol (1500), carbaryl, propoxur (500), parquat, parathion (450), aldrin (400) BHC, dimethoate (300), kelthane (175), phenol (150), formaldehyde (80), ammonia (50), Mg^{II} , Ca^{II} (600), Al^{III} , Cd^{II} , Cu^{II} (250), Fe^{II} , Fe^{III} (150), phosphate, nitrate (150), sulphate (40).

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss spectrophotometer was used. pH measurement was made with Systronics 331 pH meter.

Atrazine (Northern Minerals Limited) stock solution (1 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared in methanol; a working standard (20 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) was prepared by dilution with water.

Pyridine reagent was prepared by mixing concentrated HCl (3 ml) with freshly distilled pyridine (18 ml) and water (12 ml). A 1% (w/v) *p*-aminoben-

zoic acid (PABA) solution was prepared in 1 : 4 HCl. A 2 M NaOH solution was used. Demineralised water was used throughout. All chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Procedure : An aliquot of standard solution containing 5–20 µg of atrazine was mixed with pyridine reagent (0.2 ml). The solution was placed on a boiling water-bath for 15 min and then allowed to cool at room temperature. Then 1 ml 2 M NaOH and *p*-aminobenzoic acid solution (2 ml) were added. The solution was kept for 5 min for complete colour development and then made up to the mark with demineralised water. The absorbance was measured at 460 nm against demineralised water as reference.

Application : The proposed method has been satisfactorily applied for the determination of atrazine in grains, fruits, vegetables, soil and water. The results are shown in Table 1. For the determination of atrazine in grains and plant material, known amounts of atrazine was added to the sample, kept for 3–4 h and then extracted with chloroform (2 × 10 ml). The chloroform extract was then evaporated to dryness and the residue dissolved in methanol (25 ml). Aliquots were then analysed by the proposed method.

For the determination of atrazine in soil, known amounts of ground soil sample was spiked with known amounts of atrazine. After 3–4 h the samples were washed with methanol (2 × 10 ml). The washings were collected and made up to 25 ml with methanol. Aliquots were analysed as described above. Water sample was extracted with chloroform (2 × 25 ml) and then analysed as described above.

The present method is simple, sensitive and can be used satisfactorily for the determination of atrazine (upto 0.5 ppm) in grains, vegetables, fruits, soil and water.

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TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF ATRAZINE IN PLANT MATERIALS, SOIL AND WATER*

Sample*	Amount of atrazine Originally found µg	Amount of atrazine added µg	Amount of atrazine detected	% Detection µg
Corn ^a	–	10	9.70	97.00
		15	14.80	98.66
		20	19.20	96.00
Pineapple ^a	–	5	4.85	97.00
		10	9.88	98.80
		15	14.50	96.66
Potato ^a	–	5	4.89	97.80
		10	9.85	98.50
		15	14.80	98.66
Soil ^a	–	10	9.50	95.00
		15	14.30	95.33
		20	19.70	98.50
Field	4.50	10	14.20	97.00
Water ^b	4.22	15	18.50	95.20
	4.48	20	23.98	97.50

*Mean of 3 replicate analyses.

**Amount of sample : ^a25 g; ^b100 ml.

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